

ISic0746

I.Sicily inscription 0746

Language

Latin

Type

seat

inscription

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Amphitheatre

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Area archeologica della Neapolis, Orecchio di Dionisio e Teatro

Greco

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

hedera and cross after Sabin(i)

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---] Sabin(i) □ □ loc[us ---]

Apparatus

Text after Buonocore 1992 (EAOR)

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491636

EDCS 21900466

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7130.16 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Gentili, G.V. 1973. Studi e ricerche su l'anfiteatro di Siracusa. *Palladio. Rivista di storia dell'architettura*. 23: 3-80. At 65 fig.67, 70 no.11

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 60

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 183-185

Buonocore, M. 1992. Epigrafia anfiteatrale dell'occidente romano. III. Regiones Italiae II-V, Sicilia, Sardinia et Corsica. *Epigrafia anfiteatrale dell'occidente romano*. Rome. At 122 no.85.16, tav.XXXVIII fig.4

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